

Challenging Injustice Stretching the ‘Academic Boycott’ After War on Gaza 2023

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Abstract

The academic boycott of Israeli universities is a pivotal and contentious aspect of the broader Boycott, Divestment, Sanctions (BDS) movement, which seeks to apply pressure on Israel to change its policies and actions regarding the occupation of Palestinian territories and the treatment of Palestinians. This paper explores the academic boycott's origins, implementation, and impact, focusing on the role of Israeli universities in supporting military and state policies deemed oppressive and discriminatory against Palestinians. The history and rationale behind the academic boycott are examined, tracing its roots back to the early 2000s and highlighting key moments and subsequent international endorsements. The literature review explores the complicity of Israeli academic institutions in occupying state policies and the significant actions by global academic bodies and universities severing ties with Israeli institutions. The methodology involves a comprehensive analysis of elite university websites, boycott-related sites, mainstream news, and social media channels to assess the boycott's impact and the ongoing debate surrounding it. The discussion addresses the challenges faced by academics supporting the boycott, such as career repercussions and political backlash, and critiques the perceived double standards of boycott opponents. The conclusion focuses on Arab academics' in the East and not only in the West to get closely involved and engaged in the academic boycott movement, emphasizing their role in both raising awareness and advocating this boycott in a time when their governments are normalising relations with the Israeli apartheid regime. The authors also call for continued advocacy, education, and solidarity among academics worldwide to sustain the momentum of the academic boycott and achieve the goals of promoting Palestinian rights and ending Israeli occupation and apartheid practices.

Keywords: *Academic Boycott, Boycott Divestment Sanctions (BDS), Israeli Universities, Palestinian Rights, Academic Freedom, War on Gaza, Higher Education*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Boycott is a peaceful way of protesting and continuously disliking the behaviour of a person or an institution causing harm to others and pulling out substantial aid from that person or institution as long as they indulge in such behaviour. A boycott is defined as a limited ploy against a broader cause of injustice and under specific conditions. Direct boycott tends to change those who are directly involved with the boycott, such as the person or the institution. Indirect boycott tends to change those who are indirectly involved with the boycott, such as the country where the institution is located. (Rodin, D., & Yudkin, M. (2010)). Boycott would not be justified unless the other strategies have failed. (Chappell, T. (2001)). Boycott may be official or may be taken on its own initiative. Boycotts may be mandatory or non-mandatory. (Rodin, D., & Yudkin, M. (2010)).

The academic boycott has significant implications for Israeli academic institutions, affecting their international collaborations, funding, and academic freedom. It has also led to increased political and social efforts to counteract the BDS movement and has caused shifts in academic alliances and collaborations. BDS (2024a)

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Realising the Basis of Academic Boycott of Israel

2.1.1 History of Academic Boycott of Israel

Fraser (2008) mentioned that the origins of the Academic Boycott of Israel was launched in the spring of 2002 at the time of the Israeli offensive against Palestinians in the West Bank, which is called the Intifada. This comes after more than four decades of Israeli universities having key roles in planning, implementing and justifying Israel's occupation and apartheid policies, while maintaining a uniquely close relationship with the Israeli military. Tel Aviv University, for example, has developed tens of weapon systems and the "Dahiya doctrine" of disproportionate force employed by the Israeli military in committing war crimes against Palestinian and Lebanese civilians.

Two British academics, Steven Rose (who is Jewish) and his wife, Hilary Rose, along with 123 other mostly British academics, published an open letter in 'The Guardian' calling for a European Union moratorium on funding for grants and research contracts for Israeli universities. Within days, academics worldwide signed the petition, and similar petitions were launched in France and Australia.

The academic boycott against Israel, part of the broader Boycott, Divestment, and Sanctions (BDS) movement, continues to gain traction and face resistance. The Conference at the School of Oriental and African Studies (SOAS) at the University of London called to impose sanctions in December 2004. The focus was on resisting Israeli Apartheid strategies and principles. In April 2005, Association of University Teachers (AUT) members decided to suspend all links with Haifa and Bar-Ilan universities. BDS (2024a), BBC News (2005)

In December 2013, the council of the Native American and Indigenous Studies Association in the USA voted unanimously in favour of the academic boycott of Israel. Many coalitions who appeared over the last 25 years for Academic Boycott of Israel now believe that this is the right moment to capitalise on the opportunity when the world is condemning Israel for its atrocities.

A counterpetition to the call for a European boycott of academic and cultural ties with Israel was published on 15 April, 2002. The boycott issue was kept in the headlines when two months later, on 6 June, Mona Baker, a lecturer at UMIST University in Manchester and signatory to the Guardian letter, dismissed two Israeli academics from the editorial board of an academic journal that is published by a company she owns. BDS (2024b)

The official debate of the European government asserted that academic work should not be obstructed on political grounds, that discriminating on the basis of nationality is pernicious and will likely lead to further discrimination, and that academic discourse is crucial in keeping channels open to possibilities of peace.

The American Anthropological Association (AAA) voted in July 2023 to endorse a resolution to boycott Israeli academic institutions, with 71% of the voting members supporting the measure, Lapin (2023). This resolution focuses on suspending official ties with Israeli

academic institutions while allowing collaboration with individual Israeli scholars and students, BBC News (2005). The US Campaign for the Academic and Cultural Boycott of Israel (USACBI) is also actively encouraging US institutions to sever ties with Israeli universities, particularly opposing study abroad programs in Israel. BDS (2024b)

There have been several instances where academic and research institutions globally have chosen to sever ties with Israeli universities or companies related to Israel, often in response to calls for boycotts due to the Israeli government's policies towards Palestinians. University of Johannesburg (South Africa) was one of the earliest, where it severed its ties with Ben-Gurion University in Israel, in 2010, citing concerns over the latter's involvement in human rights abuses in Palestine. This was one of the first major universities to do so in response to a call from BDS activists.

Earlier In 2006, the National Association of Teachers in Further and Higher Education (UK) voted as a union to boycott Israeli academic institutions, though this decision faced significant legal and internal opposition. In 2013, this was followed by the American Studies Association (USA), which endorsed a boycott of Israeli academic institutions. This significant move drew both support and criticism within academic circles in the United States. In 2018, the Canadian Federation of Students managed to endorse the BDS movement, which includes support for an academic boycott of Israel. The same is done by the Irish Federation of University Teachers, which called for a boycott of Israeli academic institutions. BDS (2024a)

It is worth mentioning that taking a boycott or a divestment action might lead to significant debate and controversy, both within and outside the academic community. Institutions considering such boycotts may face legal and ethical challenges, and the situation can evolve rapidly. The University of Johannesburg in 2011 also severed links with Ben Gurion University over its complicity in Israel's human rights violations, including the theft of Palestinian water. A Human Rights Watch study reveals institutionalized racial discrimination against Palestinians throughout Israel's education system, including universities.

2.1.2 Official BDS Campaign and Efforts on Academic Boycott

The Palestinian Campaign for the Academic and Cultural Boycott of Israel (PACBI) was initiated in 2004 to contribute to the Palestinian freedom, justice, and equality struggle. It advocates for a boycott of Israeli academic and cultural institutions for their deep and persistent complicity in Israel's denial of Palestinian rights that are stipulated in international law. BDS (2024b), BDS (2024b)

PACBI is a founding member of the Palestinian BDS National Committee (BNC), and is tasked with overseeing the academic and cultural boycott aspects of BDS. The BNC, including PACBI, is committed to freedom of expression as stipulated in the United Nations International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) and, as such, rejects, on principle, boycotts of individuals based on their opinion or identity (such as citizenship, race, gender, or religion). BDS (2024a)

The current movement of boycott against Israeli institutes was launched as a part of Boycott, Divestment and Sanctions programme. This programme is used to create international pressure on Israeli institutes and universities to isolate them and put pressure on Israel to change its criteria towards the academic freedom of Palestine. Butler (2006).

Despite the attempts to argue that the boycott call was anti-Semitic, most of the USA, or UK or European calls for an institutional boycott, not one aimed at individuals of any specific nationality or ethnicity. Thus, while it would cover non-Jewish and non-Israeli academics working in Israeli universities, it would not affect Israelis working outside Israel. Moreover, the boycott calls sought to exclude individual Israeli academics from the boycott working directly with the Palestinians for peace and justice, to avoid some of those painful contradictions that the ANC's total boycott call had produced. Rose and Rose (2008)

Rose and Rose (2008) from competing in the Eurovision song contest to participating in the European Research Area, Israel is beneficially treated as a European nation. Yet its violations of international law against the Palestinians, attested in UN resolutions and in contravention of Europe's own humanitarian conventions, attract no international sanctions.

The academic boycott of Israel, following the wide-ranging boycott of South Africa that helped to publicise and end the iniquities of apartheid, aims to focus attention on issues of human rights, in the hope of securing a just peace in Palestine/Israel.

2.1.3 Screening Universities Ties with Israeli Institutions

Israel and its companies have built strong ties with academic institutions worldwide, specifically in the areas of technology, medicine, and agriculture. Many universities in the Western world are engaged with Israeli institutions through various collaborative ties, which can encompass academic, research, and cultural exchanges. These relationships are typically formed to enhance educational quality, foster international cooperation, and advance scientific research. Many of these relations are in the form of research collaborations through joint projects that involve shared interests and complementary expertise. These can range from medical research and engineering to social sciences and humanities. Collaborative research often involves shared access to funding from international grant-making bodies, which may target specific research goals that are relevant to both parties.

For example, in the United States, Harvard University is known for collaborative research projects with institutions like the Hebrew University of Jerusalem and the Technion-Israel Institute of Technology. At the same time, the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) engages in joint research initiatives and student exchange programs with several Israeli universities, including Tel Aviv University and the Technion. Stanford University also has partnerships in research and innovation with Israeli institutions.

In the United Kingdom, the University of Oxford collaborates with Israeli universities on a range of research projects across multiple disciplines. While the University of Cambridge has many research collaborations with Israeli institutions. Imperial College London is also known to have collaborative research and academic exchanges with Israeli-related affiliates.

In the rest of Europe, a number of European universities students including, Germany, Finland, Denmark, Italy, and Spain, are holding demonstrations and protests in support of the Gaza war by Israel, demanding immediate cease-fire in Gaza and cut off ties with Israeli Universities. Many of these universities' collaborations are typically aimed at advancing academic knowledge, fostering cultural understanding, and solving complex global challenges. Various European and Israeli funding agencies, including the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, fund collaborative research and innovation projects.

For example, ETH Zurich in Switzerland is partnering in research initiatives, particularly in science and technology fields, such as computer science, engineering, and environmental studies. While the University of Geneva collaborates particularly in the realms of international relations and law. In Germany, collaboration with Israeli institutions in areas of engineering, computer science, academic exchange programs, research projects and entrepreneurship programs is done through the Technical University of Munich (TUM), and Freie Universität Berlin, while the University of Heidelberg partners in research initiatives, particularly in the fields of medicine and pharmacology.

In France, École Polytechnique engages in scientific research collaborations and student exchange programs with Israeli institutions, while Sorbonne University has partnerships in humanities and social sciences, as well as scientific research. In the Netherlands, the University of Amsterdam also maintains research collaborations in economics, social sciences, and life sciences, besides the Delft University of Technology, which collaborates on engineering and technological innovations. In May 2014, faculty at the University of Amsterdam (AU) joined students in a walkout to protest Dutch police forcibly clearing student encampments and echoed their calls for cutting ties with Israeli universities. AU Faculty say since we have a centre for genocide studies on this campus, the institutions need to step up. Faculty at the University of Amsterdam joined students in a walkout to protest Dutch police forcibly clearing student encampments and echoed their calls for cutting ties with Israeli universities. Aljazeeraenglish (2024, May 14)

In Italy, the University of Bologna, engages in academic exchanges and has agreements for joint research in areas such as archaeology, history, and engineering. While the Sapienza University of Rome is known for collaborations in the sciences and humanities.

In Scandinavian countries, the University of Copenhagen (Denmark) is active in research partnerships in health sciences and life sciences, while Karolinska Institute (Sweden) collaborates on medical research and public health projects.

In Canada, the University of Toronto have partnerships in research and academic exchanges with several Israeli universities. McGill University also collaborates on research projects with Israeli institutions. While in Australia, the University of Melbourne has a history of research collaboration with Israeli universities, and there are joint research initiatives with the Australian National University. Tsinghua University (China) collaborates with Israeli universities on technology and innovation in Asia. Besides, the National University of Singapore engages in academic exchanges and joint research projects.

Academic Exchanges are another form of collaboration involving faculty members from one university teaching or conducting research at another temporarily. This exchange promotes knowledge sharing and academic networking. Many universities have agreements that allow students to study abroad at partner institutions, including those in Israel, for a semester or a year. This enriches the students' academic and cultural experiences.

Other academic collaboration forms with Israeli universities include hosting conferences, running workshops to address specific academic or societal issues, working on academic development, or working on technology transfer and commercialization. Israel is gaining lots of support to foster innovation and accelerate commercialization of research outputs. Many joint ventures in research have led to the development of patents and technologies that are commercially viable.

Leist (2017) opposed the academic boycott of Israel because he claimed that the inherently 'democratic' social institution: the university can lose its characteristics. Universities are ideal spaces of social freedom and equality, and it should not be dragged in the boycott debate. Leist believes that how one sees or justifies academic freedom depends on how one conceptualises academic work. Butler (2006).

2.1.4 Financial Ties between US Universities and Israeli Entities

Dawn (2024, 11 May) reported after the US Department of Education that colleges are required to report gifts and contracts from foreign sources. However, many universities overcome this requirement by steering money through separate foundations that work on their behalf. What is known, however, is that more than 100 US Universities have reported gifts or contracts from Israel totalling \$375 million over the past two decades.

As one example, some student protesters allege the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) has accepted more than \$11m from Israel's Defence Ministry over the past decade to work on projects related to drone navigation and missile systems. Dawn (2024) Students at the University of Michigan cite investments in companies that produce drones or warplanes used in Israel, as well as surveillance technology used at checkpoints into Gaza. University of Michigan officials, however, say they have no direct investments with Israeli companies.

These collaborations are often governed by formal agreements that outline the terms of the partnership, including the duration, objectives, and financial arrangements. They are typically driven by the shared goals of advancing knowledge, fostering cultural understanding, and addressing global challenges through joint efforts.

2.2 The Debate about the Academic Boycott

2.2.1 The Pros and Cons of Academic Boycott of Israel as seen by Academics

Proponents of the boycott argue that it responds to violations of Palestinian academic freedom and aims to pressure Israel to change its policies towards Palestinians. Opponents of the boycott, including various academic and pro-Israel organizations, argue that such measures hinder academic freedom and dialogue, which are essential for peace efforts. Critics also contend that boycotts can harm the very academics who are often critical of Israeli policies and support peace initiatives. Godlee (2007)

Critics of the boycott argue that it undermines academic freedom by preventing scholars from freely collaborating based on nationality rather than merit. This can discourage open dialogue and exchange of ideas, which are essential for academic progress. Some Israeli academics, who are often vocal critics of their government's policies, may find themselves unjustly penalized by the boycott. Nelson and Brahm (2014) proposed a detailed scholarly essay analyzing proposals to boycott Israel and the Boycott, Divestment, and Sanctions (BDS) movement versus an international cohort of scholars from Britain, Israel, and the United States who oppose the idea. Cook (2008)

The opponents also claim that this boycott has led to stigmatization and discrimination against Israeli scholars. They are facing difficulties in publishing papers, participating in international conferences, or securing collaborations, not because of their academic work but because of their affiliation with Israeli institutions. They claim that this can create a further hostile environment and discourage young scholars from pursuing academic careers.

The boycott has sparked significant political and social reactions within Israel and among its supporters globally. It has led to increased efforts by the Israeli government and pro-Israel organizations to counteract the BDS movement and promote positive aspects of Israeli academia. This includes lobbying against boycott resolutions and highlighting Israel's contributions to global research and technology.

'Boycotting might limit opportunities for students to engage in study abroad programs, research collaborations, and academic exchanges with Israeli institutions. Academics might feel responsible for the potential negative impact on their students' educational experiences, some of the pro-Israel academics claim. Educators might face challenges in accessing certain educational resources or materials produced by Israeli institutions or scholars, which can affect the quality and breadth of education they provide.

Proponents of Israeli universities argue that these institutions uphold academic freedom and are centers for critical thought and debate, including on the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. They assert that universities are not monolithic entities and host a wide range of perspectives, including those critical of government policies. The argument extends that many Israeli academics and students are actively involved in peace initiatives and movements that oppose the occupation and advocate for Palestinian rights. Godlee (2007)

The other argument is that Israeli universities often engage in collaborative research with Palestinian and international institutions aimed at promoting dialogue and understanding. These collaborations are seen as essential for building bridges and finding peaceful solutions to the conflict. Joint projects in fields such as medicine, environmental science, and technology are highlighted as examples of constructive engagement that benefits both Israelis and Palestinians, but this fact is highly debatable.

Opponents of the academic boycott believe Israeli universities contribute significantly to global scientific and technological advancements. Advocates argue that academic boycotts undermine the universal nature of academic inquiry and hinder progress in fields that can benefit humanity as a whole. Some even claim or argue that boycotting Israeli universities would negatively impact Palestinian students and academics who attend or collaborate with these institutions. Instead, fostering more inclusive academic exchanges and support for Palestinian educational institutions is proposed as a more constructive approach.

2.2.2 How the Well-known Jewish Scholar Prof. Noam Chomsky and Prof. Ilan Pappé view the Academic Boycott on Israel

Noam Chomsky believes that the defence of academic freedom is the privileging of freedom that Palestinians do not have. Protecting the academic freedom of the few is basically protecting their privileges. He believes that BDS is legitimate in trying to make an academic boycott, but still doubts whether this boycott is the right tactic. Chomsky (2017), BLEIFUSS (2015)

Noam says that the lessons from the Vietnam War show that MIT's political science department was directly involved in developing counterinsurgency techniques. MIT was also the main academic center for resistance against the War. So, he questions whether an academic boycott of MIT has been appropriate in the 1960s. With this analogy, Chomsky sees that an academic boycott on Israel is one of the least effective tactics, and it might shift attention from the oppression of the Palestinians, and in particular our crucial role in it as Americans, to the question of academic freedom. BLEIFUSS (2015)

Prof Chomsky believes one can't compare the case of South Africa's Apartheid with the Palestinian case. The educational and organizational groundwork in the case of the Apartheid regime in South Africa was carried out extensively and successfully before targeted academic boycotts were implemented. But, this is Prof Chomsky's opinion long before the devastating war started in 2023. However, he also opposes any academic appearance in Israel, which can be used for nationalistic or other propaganda purposes to cover up its occupation and denial of Palestinian human rights. He mentioned that despite his tactical differences with the BDS movement, he strongly supports the actions of BDS and continues to participate in them. Chomsky (2017), BLEIFUSS (2015)

While Professor Ilan Pappé (2018) mentioned that the persistent hold of the settlers over the Israeli society, the in-built racism of the Jewish population, the de-humanization of the Palestinians and the vested interests of the army and the industry in keeping the occupied territories, all logical reasons for academic boycott. Therefore, Pappé was astonished why the vast majority of those within the Israeli academia who regarded themselves as belonging to the progressive anti-occupation peace camp didn't sign in this academic boycott. He attributed this to their fear of losing their posts or damaging their promotions. But I suspected there were deeper reasons that do not only explain the refusal to sign, but in fact, clarify paradoxically why the academic boycott is going to be effective. Pappé (2018)

Pappé sees that 'the academia in Israel is the window shop of the Jewish society's moral and cultural self-image'. In fact, Pappé confirms that the academics in Israel are closely and almost integrally associated with the army, the political system and the industry. Therefore, Pappé now sees that rather than being a critical agency, the academics of Israel became one of the pillars of sustaining the occupation mainly by providing moral and 'scientific' explanations for the oppression in the occupied territories. Pappé (2018)

Pappé (2018) critiques Western academia as the Israeli academia is almost totally dependent on them for its financial and scholarly survival. There is a long-standing collaboration between the Israeli local campuses and the Western academia.

The academic boycott is a tool, not a vision or a wholesome strategy. Its main purpose is indeed to serve as the highway on which we can now travel in order to maximize our efforts against Israeli occupation and oppression. Thus, we should not forget that we are not all clear about or agree upon the final destination of this highway; worse, we are not totally sure about the drivers in the leading seat. Pappé (2018), Rose and Rose (2008).

2.2.3 Learning from the Academic Boycott of Apartheid South Africa

The academic boycott of South Africa during the apartheid era was part of a larger global movement aimed at isolating the South African government to pressure it to dismantle its system of racial segregation and discrimination. This boycott involved various forms of academic and cultural sanctions and was supported by numerous scholars, institutions, and countries. The academic boycott was part of the broader Boycott, Divestment, and Sanctions (BDS) movement against apartheid South Africa. It began to gain traction in the 1960s and 1970s as international opposition to apartheid grew. Buheji and Ahmed (2024).

The primary goals were to isolate South African academic institutions, prevent collaboration that could support the apartheid regime, and raise awareness about the injustices of apartheid. This was intended to pressure the South African government to end apartheid and implement equal rights for all citizens. Buheji and Hasan (2024a)

Academics and institutions outside South Africa refused to collaborate with South African universities and scholars. This included declining to attend conferences held in South Africa, rejecting invitations to give lectures or participate in research projects, and not publishing in South African academic journals. Many universities and academic associations around the world adopted formal policies prohibiting academic collaboration with South African institutions. For example 1986, the American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS, 2024) voted to impose a boycott on scientific collaboration with South Africa.

Cultural boycotts accompanied academic ones, with artists and performers refusing to visit or perform in South Africa. This cultural isolation further increased the pressure on the apartheid regime. The boycott received widespread support from international academic communities. In the United Kingdom, the British Committee for Universities of South Africa (BCUSA, 2024) significantly promoted the boycott. BDS (2024b)

Prominent academics and intellectuals, such as Nobel laureate Desmond Tutu and American sociologist Richard Falk, were vocal advocates for the boycott, lending significant credibility and visibility to the movement. Various professional associations adopted measures to enforce the boycott. The International Council for Science (ICSU), for example, suspended South Africa's membership in 1981. The academic boycott helped raise global awareness about the injustices of apartheid and increased international pressure on the South African government. It symbolized a moral stance against apartheid and galvanized other forms of activism and sanctions. The boycott was not without controversy. Critics argued that it hindered academic freedom and isolated South African academics who were opposed to apartheid. Some also felt that engagement and dialogue would be more effective than isolation.

While it is difficult to measure the direct impact of the academic boycott on dismantling apartheid, it was part of a broader set of economic, cultural, and political pressures that collectively contributed to the end of apartheid in the early 1990s. Therefore, the academic boycott of South Africa is often cited as a precedent for other academic boycott movements, such as the contemporary BDS movement against Israel. It exemplifies how academic and cultural institutions can play a role in international human rights campaigns. Newman (2016)

2.2.4 BDS Explanation about the Importance of Academic Boycott

BDS website (2024, May 16) mentioned 'Israeli universities are major, willing and persistent accomplices in Israel's regime of occupation, settler-colonialism and apartheid. They are involved in developing weapon systems and military doctrines deployed in Israel's recent war crimes in Lebanon and Gaza, justifying the ongoing colonization of Palestinian land, rationalizing gradual ethnic cleansing of indigenous Palestinians, providing moral justification for extra-judicial killings, systematically discriminating against "non-Jewish" students, and other implicit and explicit violations of human rights and international law'. To end this complicity in Israel's violations of international law, Palestinian civil society has called for an academic boycott of complicit Israeli academic institutions. Refusing to normalize oppression, many academic associations, student governments and unions as well as thousands of international academics, now support the academic boycott of Israel. Hasan (2024)

Rose and Rose (2008) reported that in July 2004, the Palestinian Campaign for the Academic and Cultural Boycott of Israel (PACBI), a Palestinian civil society group, released a statement, endorsed by campus trade unions and NGOs on the West Bank, asking for a comprehensive boycott. The Birzeit University president reinforced this call in an open letter to members of the European Parliament. In response to the PACBI call, a group of academics

working in British universities formed the British Committee for the Universities of Palestine (BRICUP) to campaign for the boycott in the universities and the academic trade unions and find practical ways to support their Palestinian colleagues.

Figure (1): Represents the Logo that calls for an Academic and Cultural Boycott against Israel

2.3 The Challenges of the Academic Boycott

2.3.1 Fears and Sacrifices of Joining Academic Boycott against Israel from the Academic Professionals

Academic professionals considering joining an academic boycott against Israel face several fears and potential sacrifices. These concerns can impact their careers, professional relationships, and personal lives now and in the future.

Many academics fear being academically isolated because they lose opportunities for collaboration, research funding, and participation in conferences, which are vital for their career advancement. Some even believe supporting the boycott might affect hiring prospects and tenure decisions, especially in institutions with strong political or financial ties to pro-Israel organizations or donors. Dawn (2024)

Boycotting Israeli academic institutions, as perceived by some academics, might strain relationships with colleagues who either oppose the boycott or have strong professional ties to Israeli academia. This can lead to professional isolation and a loss of valuable academic networks which they don't want to sacrifice. This includes the ongoing and potential collaborative projects that might be jeopardized, leading to disruptions in academic progress and innovation. Newman (2016)

Some academics might fear that their stance on the boycott could lead to censorship or self-censorship, limiting their ability to express their views and conduct research without external pressures freely. Some believe this can extend to a risk of retaliation from academic institutions, governments, or other entities opposing the boycott. This could manifest in various forms, from formal reprimands to subtle professional marginalization.

Balancing ethics and professional duty is an issue for many academics. Some academics often grapple with the ethical implications of their stance. Supporting the boycott against Israel's alleged academics may align with their personal ethics but conflict with their professional duties and obligations to their institutions and students. This dilemma is for sure irritating many academics with a consciousness about what's happening in Gaza and Palestine.

Some academics fear that they might encounter backlash from the public, political groups, and advocacy organizations that oppose the boycott, which they are not ready for. This can lead them to personal attacks, negative media coverage, and social ostracism. Others believe that their academic institutions might pressure them as faculty to avoid supporting the boycott to maintain funding, donor relations, and public standing.

2.3.2 How Israel and its Allies Fighting Back the Academic Boycott?

The Israel Lobby in the USA didn't take it easy about the academic boycott possibilities from academics or even from any higher learning institution. They started organising condemnatory statements from university presidents, vice-chancellors, and Nobel Prize winners. Full-page advertisements appeared in the New York Times.

The Jewish Board of Deputies in the UK also announced a fund dedicated to fighting the boycott through legal action that universities would face if they supported any boycott.

Leist (2017) discussed the pros and cons of the academic boycott against Israel, contesting that it depends on how one looks at the different concepts of freedom.

2.3.3 How are Israeli universities using the "loose coupling" concept to expand Academic ties with Global Universities and Overcome the Boycott?

Sapir and Kameo (2019) mentioned how Israeli universities use the concept of "loose coupling" in organizational theory, which refers to a relationship between parts of an organization that are simultaneously separate and connected. In the context of universities, including Israeli universities with their international affiliates, this concept implies a relationship where each entity retains its autonomy and distinct practices but is also linked through various coordination mechanisms.

Through many techniques, Israeli universities have managed over the years to overcome the possibility of boycotting, including establishing international affiliations with loose coupling agreements that work in several ways. Israeli universities often partner with international higher learning institutions for specific projects, such as joint research, co-authored publications, or student exchange programs. Each institution maintains its own policies, procedures, and cultural norms, but they coordinate closely on the agreed-upon projects. This allowed the Israeli universities to penetrate with high flexibility to the resources of their partners, overcoming all the types of boycott efforts.

Research collaborations may involve loosely coupled relationships where researchers from Israeli universities work with their counterparts at other international institutions. They might share data, research facilities, and expertise, but the management of resources and the direction of research can remain decentralized, allowing each party to leverage their strengths without rigid oversight from the other.

Faculty exchanges between Israeli universities and other international affiliating universities, typically based on loose coupling, allowed Israeli faculty members to teach or conduct research abroad while remaining employed by their home institution. This arrangement facilitated an exchange of knowledge and cultural insights but did not tightly integrate the faculty members into the host institution's administrative or governance structures.

Even in cases where Israeli universities have branches or offer programs abroad, these often operate with a significant degree of administrative autonomy. Decisions regarding curriculum, hiring, and daily operations might be made locally, though aligned with the broader values and standards of the parent institution. Yemini (2017).

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Based on the literature review, the authors extensively reviewed the elite universities' websites, academic boycott-related websites, and major mainstream news and social media channels, focusing on institutes throughout the USA and Europe. An analysis is carried out about what, why, how, and who of the academic boycott, besides what is the impact so far. More detailed analysis is carried out to create a comprehensive conclusion of how to sustain the momentum of this academic boycott to ensure further engagement of all the academics in the leading universities and around the world.

4.0 APPLICATION & ANALYSIS

4.1 Main List of Boycotted Israeli Universities

The colleges and universities of Israel support the stance of the Israeli government of the apartheid system against Palestinians. The universities and colleges of Israel work closely with the military establishments of Israel to develop sophisticated weapons against Palestine, Workers United (c. a). Hever (2009) mentioned seven Israeli universities that work closely with the Israeli government

- The Hebrew University, Jerusalem
- Tel-Aviv University, Tel Aviv
- Bar-Ilan University, Tel Aviv
- Haifa University, Haifa
- Technion University, Haifa
- Ben-Gurion University, Beer Sheva
- Weizman Institute, Rechovot

Israel has used Israeli universities to promote colonialism and use of apartheid against Gaza and the global academicians have been taking steps to prevent Israel from committing crimes against the people of Gaza.

Table (1): Use of Academic Institutes by Israel to Strengthen Its Occupation in Gaza

Name of Institute	Technology Developed
Tel Aviv University	Tel Aviv University developed Dahiya Doctrine named after place in Lebanon to destroy civilian population and infrastructure (Ozkan, S. (2024, March 03).)
Technion University	Technion university in association with an Israeli arms company Elbit has developed apartheid wall and surveillance technology (Ozkan, S. (2024, March 03).)
Ben-Gurion University	Ben-Gurion University partnered with Institute of Internal Security to develop military technology to assist army. (Ozkan, S. (2024, March 03).)

4.2 Status of Elite Universities in USA and Europe boycotting ties with Israel

Elite universities in the USA and Europe have generally not instituted formal policies to boycott Israeli academic institutions, but there have been significant instances of support for the Boycott, Divestment, and Sanctions (BDS) movement and related actions by individual departments, faculty members, and student groups within these institutions. The academic boycott against Israel is largely driven by various organizations and universities worldwide. Several countries have notable academic institutions and groups that have been particularly active in supporting the boycott movement. The American Anthropological Association

(AAA) has adopted a resolution to boycott Israeli academic institutions in the USA. Same is true of the University of Michigan and New York University (NYU). The major leading group in USA is the US Campaign for the Academic and Cultural Boycott of Israel (USACBI). This campaign is a significant force in the US, mobilizing academic communities to boycott Israeli institutions. Lapin (2023).

In the University of California, Berkeley, for example, some departments and faculty members at UC Berkeley have expressed support for the BDS movement, although the university as a whole has not adopted a formal boycott policy. At Harvard University, numerous events and discussions have been hosted by student groups and faculty members who are sympathetic to the BDS movement.

Columbia University's student body also voted in favour of a referendum supporting the divestment from companies involved in Israeli activities in Palestine. However, the university administration did not adopt the measure. New York University (NYU) has seen active participation from various student groups and faculty in support of the academic boycott. Therefore, the Department of Social and Cultural Analysis pledged non-cooperation with NYU's Tel Aviv program in 2019. Hurwitz (2109)

Cambridge University has had individual faculty members express support for the boycott, but no official university-wide policy has endorsed the academic boycott of Israel. Same case applies to the University of Oxford, which debates and expressions of support for the BDS movement among its faculty and students, though it has not adopted an institutional boycott.

The BDS movement started to have more grassroots support in many elite universities, with student unions and specific academic departments often leading the charge. Despite this support, few if any, elite universities have formally adopted comprehensive boycott policies. Most official stances emphasize the importance of academic freedom and dialogue over boycotts.

Table (2): List of Organizations Supporting Academic Boycott of Israel

Organization Name	News About Academic Boycott of Israel
Lecturer Union of UK	69,000 members of the union have urged to boycott of Israeli universities that are not distancing themselves from the government policies. BBC News (2006).
Association of University Teachers	Boycott University of Haifa, Bar-Ilan University and Hebrew university of Jerusalem. BBC News (2005).
National Association of Teachers in Further and Higher Education (NATFHE)	In May 2006, NATFHE passed a resolution to boycott Israeli universities that do not speak against their government. Library of Congress (2006)
University and College Union	University and College Union, one of the largest trade unions for academics with around 120,000 members, severed all ties with Histadrut, who had supported the attack on Gaza by Israel. Paul (2010).
The Coordination des Scientifiques pour une Paix Juste au Proche-Orient,	French academicians published a letter in the Guardian to boycott scientific institutes. Le Monde (2003).
California University	Sonoma State University, a part of California University, has disassociated itself from any engagement with Israeli Universities. Maltz (2024)
Free University of Brussels	A group of students encamped inside the hall of the university, asking for the academic boycott of Israel. Rasquinho (2024).
Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology (RMIT), Australia	The contract with Israeli arms manufacturer Elbit System was ended by Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology, Australia. Ozkan (2024)

OsloMet University, Norway	OsloMet University, Norway terminated the exchange program between the University of Haifa and OsloMet University. Ozkan (2024)
Bergen Institute of Architecture, Norway	Two alliance agreements between Bergen Institute of Architecture, Norway and Bezalel Academy of Arts was ended by between Bergen Institute of Architecture, Norway. Ozkan (2024)
University of Southeast Norway (USN)	The cooperation agreement between the University of Haifa & Hadassah Academic College, Israel and the University of Southeast,Norway, was ended by the University of Southeast,Norway. Ozkan (2024)
American Anthropological Association (AAA)	American Anthropological Association (AAA) has decided to cut ties with Israeli institutes. Lapin (2023)
UK Societies for Middle Eastern Studies	UK Societies passed a resolution for Middle Eastern Studies, having its headquarters at Leeds to academically boycott Israeli Institutes. The Times of Israel (2019)

4.3 The Academic Boycott Spreading since the War on Gaza in October 2023

The University and College Union (UCU) has a history of supporting motions for academic boycotts against Israel in the United Kingdom. Although not all motions have passed, the union has been a strong advocate for the BDS movement.

In South Africa, the University of Johannesburg in 2011 severed its ties with Israel's Ben-Gurion University, marking one of the first significant academic boycott actions by a major university. Also, the South African Union of Students has been vocal in supporting the academic boycott and broader BDS movement against Israel.

In Ireland, the student union of Trinity College Dublin, in 2018, voted to support the BDS movement, including an academic boycott of Israeli institutions. Faculty members from various Irish universities have also expressed support for the boycott.

In Canada, York University and the University of Toronto both have seen significant student and faculty support for the BDS movement, including calls for academic boycotts of Israeli institutions. The Norwegian University of Science and Technology also started in 2009 an academic boycott proposal, which reflected growing support within the academic community in Norway. In Belgium, several university faculty members and student groups support the academic boycott and broader BDS initiatives.

These regions and institutions exemplify the global nature of the academic boycott movement against Israel. While not all countries have officially endorsed the boycott, significant segments of the academic community within these countries have been leading the charge. The movement is characterized by its grassroots nature, with various academic and student groups driving the agenda forward.

5.0 SCREENING THE IMPACT OF ACADEMIC BOYCOTT

5.1 How are Academic Boycotts straining Israeli Universities?

Maira (2018) reviewed the broader history of boycotts in the United States as well as in Palestine and shows how it has evolved into a transnational social movement that has spurred profound intellectual and political shifts. It explores the movement's implications for antiracist, feminist, queer, and academic labour organizing and examines the boycott in the context of debates about Palestine, Zionism, race, rights-based politics, academic freedom, decolonization, and neoliberal capitalism.

The impact of the academic boycott on Israel has been affecting both its academic institutions and broader societal perceptions. The boycott has led to the isolation of Israeli universities in various international academic forums and collaborations. For instance, some academic associations, like the American Anthropological Association, have passed resolutions to boycott Israeli academic institutions, barring them from participating in certain academic exchanges and conferences. This limited the opportunities for Israeli scholars to engage with their international peers and can hinder collaborative research efforts.

These boycotts have also started to impact the funding for research and academic programs. International collaborations often come with financial grants and resources. The withdrawal or reduction of such collaborations can affect the financial stability of Israeli universities, potentially leading to reduced research output and academic development. Dawn (2024)

The outcome of this academic boycott has made Israel seek to shift new academic alliances, where the Israeli institutions build new partnerships or strengthen existing ones outside the realms affected by the boycott. This can sometimes lead to stronger bilateral collaborations with countries and institutions that oppose the boycott, but it also means that Israeli academia may become less integrated into broader global academic networks.

Rose and Rose (2008) mention that many Israeli academics are complicit the illegal settlements and need to be strained from doing so. These authors mentioned the Bar-Ilan University, which broke its links with such settlements in the wake of the European boycott debates in 2005. That university fostered the work of the illegal College of Judea and Samaria in Ariel, in the illegally occupied West Bank.

Many Israeli universities are also complicit in discrimination against Arab students. Rose and Rose (2008) many Arab-Palestinian students are suffering because of the conditions created around them. Some universities are built or extended on an illegal seizure of Palestinian lands; the most known example is the Hebrew University in Jerusalem in Tel-Aviv. Cook (2008)

5.2 Importance of Academic Boycotts on Other Economic and Cultural Boycotts

In today's knowledge economy, academic boycott matters. The production cycle of knowledge besides science and technology requires areas in which the flow of academic collaborations between Israeli and advanced countries is not obstructed.

Today, Israel is one of the most advanced countries in biotechnology, embryonic stem cell research, nanotechnology, and informatics because of the free flow of knowledge production between Israel and Europe and its related funding. Many of these industries are funded by Western industry and their military.

The academic boycott is also expected to affect Israel's advancement in intellectual property, which is based on both academic and economic empowerment. For Israel, academic institutions play a main role in keeping its economic status in the global market since all the informatics and biotechnology advancement research is dependent on the empowerment of research. Therefore, the academic boycott would surely bring noise to the Israeli economy.

As Nelson Mandela said 'boycotts are a tactic in political struggle'. Depending on the circumstances, they may or may not be appropriate or effective. When the ANC, called for a total boycott of the apartheid South African Regime, the academic moved the sporting boycott of apartheid, which seized the media in Britain at that time. This dramatically raised public

awareness and, as one of many strands contributing to the pressure for change, led ultimately to UN sanctions.

The Israeli's are worried about the cascading development that the academic boycott could bring, starting from the furious debates it could generate among intellectuals in social media, which would draw massive media attention and nourish the rising anger of civil society worldwide. Therefore, the 'Likud cabinet' established an anti-boycott committee with Binyamin Netanyahu as its chair. For Israel, the threat was too great to be left to the university administrations to respond.

5.3 Example of a Country-Wide Spreading Academic Boycott from Spain

The Conference of University Rectors in Spain (CRUE) has decided to suspend collaboration agreements with Israeli universities and research centers that do not firmly commit to peace and comply with international humanitarian law. This move aligns with international legal bodies, including the International Court of Justice and the UN, which have condemned Israel's actions in Gaza and called for sanctions. Buheji and Hasan (2024b)

No Israeli universities meet the required conditions, as they are documented to support the Israeli military and its operations against Palestinians. Haidar Eid, a professor in Gaza, noted that this decision is a crucial step in holding Israel accountable for its actions, which have included the destruction of Palestinian educational institutions.

This decision comes amid student protests across Spanish universities and is part of a broader call by Palestinian universities for international academic institutions to isolate Israeli universities. The University of Barcelona also recently voted to end ties with complicit Israeli academic entities. PACBI (2024)

PACBI urges other international universities to follow this example to end collaborations with Israeli institutions that support the occupation and apartheid regime.

Rigg (2024) mentioned that Spanish universities have agreed to review ties with Israeli universities and research centres and suspend collaboration agreements with those that “have not expressed a firm commitment to peace and compliance with international humanitarian law. According to the governing board of the Conference of Rectors of Spanish Universities (CRUE), they also vowed to intensify co-operation with Palestinian research and higher learning institutions. CRUE, representing 76 private and public universities in Spain, stated its “deep regret for the very serious events that are currently taking place in the Gaza Strip”. The statement said: “Spanish universities have already expressed and reaffirmed on several occasions their permanent commitment to peace, coexistence and justice, and defence of international law, which does not prevent us from once again being deeply moved by the worsening of the conflict and the painful consequences it is having for the Palestinian population.” “We endorse the sentiments of our campuses and the demands that they are making to ensure that measures are adopted at different levels to put a stop to the escalation of violence that is taking place. Consequently, we demand the immediate and definitive cessation of military operations by the Israeli army, as well as any action of a terrorist nature, and the liberation of the people kidnapped by Hamas,” the statement noted.

It added that the State of Israel should allow entry into Gaza of any humanitarian aid that can be provided to meet the civilian population's emergency needs, and that international bodies undertake as soon as possible to reconstruct and rehabilitate the Gaza Strip.

CRUE committed to expanding “our cooperation, volunteering and care programs for the refugee population”, it stated. The rectors’ body also committed to “ensure that in the exercise of free expression, equally reprehensible conduct of anti-Semitism or Islamophobia does not occur, as well as any other hateful behaviour within the university communities”.

The Coordinator of Student Representatives in Public Universities (CREUP), an umbrella organisation for Spanish student unions, representing more than one million students in 31 public universities, has demanded that the Minister of Science, Innovation and Universities, to take action to improve the situation of university students in Palestine and put an end to any type of collaboration with Israel, in particular in the Spanish university system. Since the genocide is taking place in Gaza, the students are demanding that Spanish universities cut all agreements and then, if necessary, review it, but in the first instance to cut all of them.

The university rectors’ statement was made a day after Israeli forces began a military operation in Rafah. The current wave of protests in Spain to the historical context of student battles going back to the University of Barcelona protest strikes in November 1913 and protests against Franco’s repression in the 1950s and 60s, arguing that the fight for justice and freedom has been a constant in the history of Spanish universities. It is part of La Sexta Spanish culture. Buheji and Hasan (2024b)

6.0 NEXT STEPS TO ACCELERATE THE IMPACT OF THE ACADEMIC BOYCOTT

6.1 Increasing the Momentum of the Academic Boycott

The academic boycott against Israel has seen notable increases in activity, particularly following any escalations in Gaza and Palestine. In July 2023, the American Anthropological Association (AAA) voted to endorse a resolution to boycott Israeli academic institutions, with 71% of voting members in favour. This decision was influenced by recent reports on apartheid and increased abuses of Palestinian academic freedom by Israel. Buheji et al. (2024)

US Campaign for the Academic and Cultural Boycott of Israel (USACBI) has intensified its calls for academic boycotts, particularly urging US institutions to end study abroad programs in Israel. They argue that participation in such programs perpetuates the ongoing violation of Palestinian academic and human freedoms.

In New York University (NYU) over 50 campus groups and an academic department pledged not to affiliate with NYU’s Tel Aviv academic center, citing solidarity with Palestinian academic freedom. While in the University of Michigan, some instructors declined to write letters of recommendation for students wishing to study in Israel, aligning with the academic boycott principles.

In Pitzer College, the faculty and a mixed student/faculty decision-making body called for suspending the college’s study-abroad program with the University of Haifa. Although the college president vetoed this decision, it highlighted the growing support for academic boycotts on campuses.

The academic boycott has garnered endorsements from various academic associations and individual scholars, who argue that it is a necessary response to the violations of Palestinian rights. These endorsements have increased in frequency and intensity following the recent Gaza conflict. Several academic bodies and prominent academics have issued statements condemning Israeli actions and supporting the boycott. For instance, the American Studies

Association and the Middle East Studies Association have been vocal in their support for the BDS movement. These examples illustrate the growing momentum of the academic boycott against Israel, particularly as a response to the heightened conflict and humanitarian crises in Gaza. The movement seeks to pressure Israel into changing its policies towards Palestinians through the leverage of academic institutions and collaborations.

6.2 Why would academic boycotts have a chance of success now?

The boycott of academics might make a lot of difference and would have more chance of spreading now more than ever since now people are ready to take a lifetime decision in express of despair and anger at what they are seeing in social media every day. Also, any unfair treatment of academics would attract international civil society, including academics.

The movement of Gen-Z in the West towards boycott and divestment in their universities using social media would give this academic boycott more chance to spread, as this generation would soon also be leaders in these academic institutions or the community. Buheji (2024)

The bigger picture is to align the academic boycott with academic unions, which would also lead to an economic boycott of Israeli products. This academic boycott should be aligned with the musicians, writers and filmmakers boycott that is formed under the cultural boycott who are actively disinvesting with Israel. Also, this can be aligned with the doctors' group works to eject Israel from the World Medical Association. Rose and Rose (2008)

Universities and their communities are coming together to emphasize divestment from companies that support Israeli activities in Palestine through various organized efforts. These efforts include student-led campaigns, faculty endorsements, official resolutions, and collaborative networks across institutions. For example, the American Studies Association (ASA) and other academic associations have voted to endorse the academic boycott of Israeli institutions. These votes often involve extensive discussion and debate among faculty members and are a significant form of academic support for the BDS movement.

The National Students for Justice in Palestine (NSJP) organizes annual conferences that bring together students from various universities to strategize and share resources for BDS campaigns. These conferences often lead to coordinated actions and campaigns across multiple campuses. US Campaign for the Academic and Cultural Boycott of Israel (USACBI) mobilizes also faculty and students across the United States to support the academic boycott. They provide resources, organize events, and issue statements that unify various academic communities in their support for divestment and boycott initiatives. However, the University of Michigan as a whole has yet to adopt a formal divestment policy. However, the actions of faculty members refusing to write recommendation letters for study in Israel reflect a significant level of support for the boycott within the academic community.

The emphasis on divestment in university communities involves a combination of student activism, faculty support, collaborative networks, and sometimes official institutional actions. These efforts collectively work to pressure universities to reconsider their investments and affiliations with companies and institutions alleged to be complicit in human rights violations in Palestine. The movement is characterized by a broad coalition of students, faculty, and academic associations coming together to support the principles of the BDS movement through various organized strategies and actions.

6.3 Focusing on the Double Standard of Those Opposing the Academic Boycott

The debate over the academic boycott of Israeli universities, as advocated by the Boycott, Divestment, Sanctions (BDS) movement, often includes accusations of a double standard by those who oppose the boycott. While some still defend the academic freedom of Israeli universities, many academics are closing their eyes and minds about this ethically driven academic boycott. They continue to be silent about the War on Gaza and the various attacks by Israel on the Palestinian universities.

Critics argue that the BDS movement unfairly singles out Israel while ignoring human rights abuses and conflicts in other countries. They point to the lack of academic boycotts against countries with comparable or worse records on human rights. This selective targeting is seen as indicative of a double standard, raising questions about the underlying motivations of the boycott movement.

Opponents of the boycott argue that it infringes upon academic freedom by restricting the free exchange of ideas and collaboration across borders. They assert that academic boycotts undermine the universal principles of education and research. The emphasis on academic freedom is often highlighted as inconsistent when applied selectively, criticizing the BDS movement for potentially stifling dissenting voices within Israeli academia who may be supportive of Palestinian rights.

It is argued that an academic boycott could inadvertently harm Palestinian students and academics who attend or collaborate with Israeli universities. These institutions sometimes offer programs and resources that are not available in Palestinian territories.

Critics assert that rather than isolating Israeli universities, efforts should be made to support and enhance educational opportunities for Palestinians, promoting cooperation rather than division.

Israeli universities are home to many academics and students who are actively engaged in peace efforts and critical of Israeli government policies. Boycotting these institutions could silence important voices for change and undermine initiatives aimed at fostering dialogue and understanding.

Proponents of the academic boycott argue that the focus on Israel is due to its specific and ongoing occupation of Palestinian territories and the systemic nature of the oppression, which they liken to apartheid. They believe that targeted pressure on Israel can lead to meaningful change. They also point out that other countries and situations have their own forms of international pressure and activism, tailored to their specific contexts. Focusing on Israel, the international community can address a specific and urgent case of occupation and apartheid, aligning with broader principles of human rights.

7.0 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

7.1 The Challenge is overcoming the fears of the Level of Sacrifice and Faith of Conscious

Joining an academic boycott against Israel involves significant fears and sacrifices for academic professionals, including career repercussions, strained professional relationships, threats to academic freedom, ethical dilemmas, impacts on students, and political and social backlash. These concerns make the decision to support the boycott a complex and deeply personal one, balancing professional responsibilities with ethical and political beliefs.

7.2 Synthesis of how Israeli Universities are part of the Colonial Apartheid Regime

The role of Israeli universities differs in the level of the involvement and impact of these institutions on both the Palestinians and how they are part of the Israeli regime in relevance to research and development for military purposes, besides the role of the academic programs and policies that target to normalize and legitimize the occupation.

Israeli universities, particularly institutions like the Technion which Israel Institute of Technology, are often cited for their collaboration with the Israeli military. Critics argue that research and development conducted in these universities directly support military operations, including those in the occupied Palestinian territories. The technologies developed in collaboration with universities are sometimes used in surveillance, security, and defence systems, contributing to controlling and monitoring Palestinian populations.

Some universities offer programs and courses that critics say normalize and legitimize the occupation. These programs may include studies in security, defence, and counter-terrorism, which are often linked to the military-industrial complex. There are allegations that certain academic policies and practices discriminate against Palestinian students, limiting their access to higher education and academic resources.

The other allegation of these Israeli academic institutions is the expansion of university campuses, particularly in East Jerusalem and other contested areas, is seen by some as a form of land appropriation. These expansions can involve the displacement of Palestinian communities and the appropriation of land considered illegal under international law.

7.3 Arab Academics' role in supporting Academic Boycotts

Arab academics in the Western world played a significant role in supporting the academic boycott of Israeli universities as part of the broader Boycott, Divestment, Sanctions (BDS) movement. Their involvement is driven by various motivations, including solidarity with Palestinians, opposition to the occupation, and a desire to promote justice and equality.

These Arab academics living in the West have been at the forefront of articulating the rationale behind the academic boycott. They use their platforms to raise awareness about the situation in Palestine and to call for international solidarity. Therefore, Institutions such as the Palestinian Campaign for the Academic and Cultural Boycott of Israel (PACBI) have been instrumental in organizing and promoting the boycott, with significant input from Arab scholars.

However, one could notice that there is a weak or none-studied role of Arab Academics living in the Middle East. As their countries start to normalise relations with Israel, they should have a clear stand about the academic boycott. These locally based Arab academics should educate themselves about the complicity of Israeli academic institutions in the occupation and call on their colleagues worldwide to join the boycott. This boycott should be announced from notable signatories include professors, researchers, and intellectuals from various Arab countries who lend their credibility and influence to the movement.

This paper calls for such local Arab academics to contribute to the academic discourse by publishing further research that supports the principles of the boycott. This includes analyses of Israeli policies, and the impact of the occupation. This should help the Arab community in the East be more aware of the possible intersections between academia and politics, emphasizing how Israeli universities could be boycotted even if the Arab normalising governments want the opposite.

Arab academics also need to engage in educational initiatives aimed at informing students and the public about the academic boycott. This includes organizing conferences, seminars, and workshops focusing on the boycott's ethical and political dimensions. They could collaborate with international scholars to create curricula and resources that support the goals of the BDS movement.

By participating in and organizing international conferences and forums, Arab academics help create cross-border academic networks that facilitate the exchange of ideas and strategies related to the boycott. These networks also serve as platforms for sharing experiences and best practices, enhancing the effectiveness of the boycott campaign.

Despite the fact that some Arab academics might face political repression and risks associated with openly supporting the boycott, they should continue to advocate for the movement, demonstrating significant courage and commitment.

7.4 Implications of this Study

This study shows that academic boycott of Israeli universities is a critical aspect of the broader Boycott, Divestment, Sanctions (BDS) movement, aiming to pressure Israel to change its policies regarding the occupation and treatment of Palestinians. This paper explored the boycott's origins, its significant moments, and its impacts on Israeli academic institutions.

Arab academics, especially in Western institutions, have been vital in advocating for the boycott and raising global awareness. However, greater participation from Arab academics in the Middle East is needed, especially given regional normalization with Israel. One should appreciate that academics supporting the boycott face challenges such as career risks and political backlash, yet the boycott remains a potent tool for promoting Palestinian rights and ethical academic practices.

The academic boycott's potential to influence broader economic and cultural boycotts is significant, drawing parallels with the successful boycott of apartheid South Africa. The isolation and financial strain on Israeli universities highlight the boycott's effectiveness in creating pressure for change. Thus, sustaining the academic boycott's momentum requires ongoing advocacy, education, and global solidarity. The academic community can significantly support Palestinian rights and challenge occupation and apartheid structures through informed and ethical actions.

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